

ETYMOLOGY AND DERIVATION IN MEDICAL VOCABULARY: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH, UZBEK, AND KARAKALPAK

Matkurbanova Yulduz Urazimbetovna,
Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh
Teacher of the interfaculty department of foreign
languages

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Abstract: *Medical terminology across languages reflects the historical evolution of science and language. This article provides a comparative analysis of the etymology and derivation of medical terms in English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak. By tracing the origins of common medical terms and analyzing their derivational processes, the study highlights the linguistic patterns that shape medical vocabulary. The findings reveal both universal and language-specific approaches to incorporating foreign roots, adapting terms, and forming new medical lexicons in each language.*

Keywords: *Etymology, medical vocabulary, derivation, English, Uzbek, Karakalpak, linguistic adaptation, historical linguistics*

Introduction

Medical terminology plays a crucial role in healthcare communication, and understanding how medical terms are derived and adapted across languages is essential for cross-linguistic communication in the medical field. The roots of many medical terms are based on classical languages, particularly Latin and Greek, but languages such as Uzbek and Karakalpak, with their Turkic roots, employ unique derivational processes to adapt medical concepts. The presence of these processes reflects historical interactions, including the influence of Russian and Persian on these languages.

This article explores the etymology and derivational processes involved in the formation of medical terms in English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak. The goal is to compare how medical terms in these three languages have evolved, focusing on the linguistic sources of medical vocabulary and the strategies employed to adapt foreign terms to local linguistic structures.

Methods

A comparative etymological and morphological analysis was conducted on a selection of 100 common medical terms from each of the three languages. The terms were gathered from medical dictionaries, textbooks, and journals. The analysis focused on tracing the origins of the terms, examining both their roots and their derived forms. Emphasis was placed on identifying the sources of these terms (e.g., Latin, Greek, Russian) and the linguistic processes—such as affixation, root modification, and phonological adaptation—used to integrate them into each

language's medical lexicon.

Results

The study revealed several key findings regarding the etymology and derivation of medical terms in each language:

1. English:

English medical terminology has deep roots in Latin and Greek, which have significantly influenced its lexicon. Many terms, such as cardiology (from Greek "kardia" for heart + "logia" for study), pathology (from Greek "pathos" for disease + "logia" for study), and hematology (from Greek "haima" for blood + "logia"), are derived from these classical languages. English medical terminology also frequently uses Latin prefixes and suffixes, such as hyper- (excessive), hypo- (below), and -itis (inflammation). For instance, arthritis (from Greek "arthron" for joint + "itis" for inflammation) clearly demonstrates the use of these suffixes.

Additionally, many medical terms are formed through Latinization and Grecization processes, where native terms are replaced with Greek or Latin equivalents. A prime example is gastroenterology (from Greek "gaster" for stomach + "enteron" for intestines + "logia" for study). The continued usage of Latin and Greek roots is integral to the English medical lexicon.

2. Uzbek:

Uzbek medical terminology is a blend of foreign borrowings and native Turkic affixes. Some terms are directly borrowed from Russian or English, while others have been adapted using Uzbek linguistic structures.

For example, the term микробиология (microbiology) is borrowed from Russian but adapted into Uzbek through the native suffix -шунаслик (meaning "science" or "study of"). This suffix is commonly used to form fields of study, such as фармакология (pharmacology) becoming фармакологияшунаслик (the science of pharmacology).

In addition to borrowing, Uzbek frequently modifies foreign roots to fit its phonological system. For example, the English term cardiology becomes кардиология in Uzbek, with slight modification to suit Uzbek phonology, particularly regarding vowel harmony and syllable structure. The consonant clusters present in the English term are softened, which is a typical phonological adaptation in Uzbek.

Hybrid Forms: A significant number of Uzbek medical terms involve blending foreign roots with native suffixes. For example, педиатрия (pediatrics) becomes педиатрияшунаслик, which combines the Greek root with the Uzbek suffix -

шунаслик.

3. Karakalpak:

Karakalpak, like Uzbek, adapts foreign terms but also makes more extensive phonological changes to suit its native sound system. For instance, the term геронтология (gerontology) is borrowed from Russian, but in Karakalpak, it may be pronounced as геронтология while still using the Russian form in writing.

Phonologically, Karakalpak simplifies consonant clusters or modifies syllable stress to make the term easier to pronounce for native speakers.

Native Derivational Affixes: Karakalpak medical terms are often adapted with native derivational affixes. For example, the term дерматология (dermatology) is transformed into дерматологиялик (dermatology-related field), using the Karakalpak suffix -лик, which denotes a professional or academic field.

Loan Translations: Karakalpak also uses calques or loan translations to create medical terms. For example, the term микробиология (microbiology) can be translated as микробтану (micro-study), where the meaning is retained, but the term is adapted using native words instead of borrowing directly from Russian or English.

Discussion

The comparative analysis of medical terms in English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak highlights both universal trends and language-specific strategies in the adaptation of medical terminology. These strategies stem from the historical evolution of each language and reflect different linguistic priorities.

1. **Borrowing and Adaptation:** English has a long history of borrowing Latin and Greek roots, and these languages remain the primary source of its medical vocabulary. This borrowing process is relatively straightforward, with minimal alteration to the roots. In contrast, Uzbek and Karakalpak, while also borrowing foreign terms, make significant adjustments to these terms to maintain phonological and morphological consistency with their native linguistic structures.

2. **Phonological Adaptation:** Uzbek and Karakalpak demonstrate a strong tendency to modify the phonology of borrowed terms to suit their native sound systems. For example, the consonant clusters in English medical terms, such as cardiology, are simplified in both Uzbek (кардиология) and Karakalpak (кардиология). These phonological changes make medical terms easier to pronounce and more accessible to native speakers. The use of vowel harmony in Uzbek also plays a role in the adaptation process, as foreign terms are modified to fit this phonological pattern.

3. **Etymological Sources and Influences:** The etymological sources of

medical terms in Uzbek and Karakalpak reflect the historical influences of Russian and Persian in the region. Russian has been a major conduit through which Western medical knowledge was introduced to Central Asia, and this is evident in the large number of Russian-derived terms in both languages. The historical role of the Russian Empire and Soviet Union in the region is reflected in the widespread use of Russian medical terms, which are often adapted with native Turkic morphological structures.

4. **Language-Specific Derivational Strategies:** Both Uzbek and Karakalpak use native affixes to create medical terms, which helps maintain linguistic continuity. The use of affixes like *-шунаслик* in Uzbek and *-лик* in Karakalpak ensures that new medical terms fit the morphological patterns of each language. These affixes are typically used to denote fields of study or professional domains, and they help speakers understand the meaning of complex medical terms by breaking them down into recognizable components.

Conclusion

The comparative analysis of medical terminology in English, Uzbek, and Karakalpak demonstrates how etymology and derivational processes shape the development of medical terms in each language. While English relies heavily on its classical roots in Latin and Greek, Uzbek and Karakalpak employ native derivational strategies to adapt foreign terms. The integration of medical terms through phonological adjustments and morphological processes ensures that medical vocabulary is accessible to speakers of each language while maintaining its scientific precision.

Further research could explore additional Turkic languages or delve deeper into the role of Russian as a linguistic bridge in the development of medical terminology in Central Asia. Additionally, investigating the practical impact of these derivational patterns on healthcare delivery and education in multilingual contexts would offer valuable insights.

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